

Notas breves

First record of *Troглоconcha* sp. (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Larocheidae) in the Mediterranean Sea

Primera cita de *Troглоconcha* sp. (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Larocheidae) en el mar Mediterráneo

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INTRODUCTION

The family Larocheidae Finlay, 1927 includes three genera: *Larochea* Finlay, 1927 (Type genus), *Larocheopsis* Marshall, 1993 and *Troглоconcha* Kase & Kano, 2002, whose species are distributed from the Indian Ocean and the Red Sea to the Central Pacific (KASE & KANO, 2002; GEIGER, 2012: 1185). The typical habitat of *Troглоconcha* has been reported in submarine caves, but also blocks of hardground, foraminiferal sand, coral sand, in cavities and crevices with live sponges and bryozoans.

The morphological features of our sample persuaded us of assigning it to the genus *Troглоconcha* to which belong species with minute and fragile shells, umbilicate, with a smooth protoconch, a turbiniform teleoconch that is laterally expanded, with rounded whorls covered

with a reticulate sculpture, without an anal slit, having a large aperture and without an internal inner septum.

It is difficult for us to give a definite explanation for the presence of this shell belonging to the genus *Troглоconcha* which has a so remote known range and is found there in shallow water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A single shell of *Troглоconcha* sp., in very good condition, was collected in April 1999, off the isle of Capraia (Tuscan Archipelago), at a depth of 700 m ; shell height 1.05 mm, shell width 0,98 mm. The shell is deposited in the private collection of Francesco Giusti (Livorno).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Superfamily SCISSURELLOIDEA Gray, J.E., 1847
Family LAROCHEIDAE Finlay, 1927
Genus *Troглоconcha* Kase & Kano, 2002

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Figure 1. *Trogloconcha* sp., off isle of Capraia, Tuscan Arch., 700 m. A, B: detail of the protoconch; C: dorsal view; D: frontal view.

Figure 1. *Trogloconcha* sp., frente a la isla de Capraia, archipiélago toscano, 700 m. A, B: detalle de la protoconcha; C: vista dorsal; D: vista frontal.

Trogloconcha sp. (Figure 1A-D)

Description of our shell: Shell small (1.05x0.98 mm), fragile, last round very large, as wide as high (width/height ratio about 1). Protoconch approximately 240 µm in diameter, 0.75 whorl, smooth. Aperture round, large with margin curved, interrupted at base of previous whorl, outer lip thin and sharp, no apertural varix. Teleoconch with 1.75 whorls, with rapidly increasing diameter. Sculpture with dense axials and spirals; the axials approximately 70 in number on the body whorl, stronger than the spirals, their intersection producing a fine reticulate pattern. A tiny opening in the umbilicus. No selenizone, slit, or foramen. Colour opaque white.

Remarks: Belonging to the genus *Trogloconcha* there are some species very similar to our shell, such as *Trogloconcha ohashii* Kase & Kano, 2002, which however has a much wider, funnel-like umbilicus and the axials and spirals of equal strength. *Trogloconcha tessellata* Kase & Kano, 2002 has a tiny opening in the umbilicus, though normally the umbilicus is fully closed, and the axials are stronger than the spirals. The umbilicus may be more or less open, we do not consider this a significant character, and attribute it solely to intraspecific variability. Our shell differs from *T. marshalli* (Lozouet, 1998), fossil of the late Oligocene (Chattian) collected in the Aquitaine basin, France, mainly by the

narrower shell, lower expansion rate, and having weaker spirals towards the umbilicus. Additionally, the type of *marshalli* lacks points at intersection of axials and spirals, and has a slight opening of the umbilicus. The measurements of the shell collected off the isle of Capraia are in the range of shell diameter of the species mentioned above, but based on these main features we are unable to determine with certainty to which species our shell belongs. The inclusion in genus *Trogloncha* was confirmed to us by Dr. Geiger (pers. com.) after seeing the photos of our sample.

This study records the presence of one shell of *Trogloncha* sp. originating in the Indian Ocean where they have been recorded widely. However one species, *T. tessellata*, that is mainly found in shallow water, although there are some records from 300-500 m depth (Geiger pers. com.), was recently collected along the Israeli coast of the Red Sea (off Marsat Abu Samra, 49 m). Although transport of shallow water micros is not uncommon, we considered it very unli-

kely that our shell had entered the Mediterranean probably through the Suez Canal, or as a case of ballast-water transport.

Another hypothesis, the more likely, is that our shell may be a fossil belonging probably to the late Pleistocene age (last glacial), at a time when the deep Mediterranean sea was very rich. In the sample of sediment were present some species of Thecosomata and other molluscs represented by some fossil shells of probable last glacial age, including:

Limacina retroversa (Fleming, 1823)

Helicinooides inflata (D'Orbigny, 1836)

Diacria trispinosa (Blainville, 1821)

Pseudamussium peslutrae (Linnaeus, 1771)

In particular, the common *Limacina retroversa* (Fleming, 1823) considered to be a typical indicator species for colder climates, has been repeatedly recorded from the Pleistocene sediments in the eastern Mediterranean (CORSELLI & GRECCHI, 1990; BONFITTO, OLIVERIO, SABELLI AND TAVIANI; JANSSEN, 2012).

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BONFITTO A., OLIVERIO M., SABELLI B. AND TAVIANI M. 1994. A quaternary deep-sea marine molluscan assemblage from East Sardinia (Western Tyrrhenian Sea). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 30 (5-9): 141-157.
- CORSELLI C. AND GRECCHI G. 1990. Considerazioni sui Thecosomata attuali del Bacino Mediterraneo. *Lavori della Società Italiana di Malacologia*, 24: 120-130.
- GEIGER D.L. 2012. Monograph of the little slit shells. Volume 1. Introduction, Scissurellidae. pp. 1-728. Volume 2. Anatomidae, Larocheidae, Depressizonidae, Sutilizonidae, Temnocinclidae. pp. 729-1291. *Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History Monographs*, 7.
- JANSSEN A.J. 2012. Late Quaternary to Recent holoplanktonic Mollusca (Gastropoda) from bottom samples of the eastern Mediterranean Sea: systematics, morphology. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 48 (suppl. 9): 1-105.
- KASE T. AND KANO Y. 2002. *Trogloncha*, a new genus of larocheine Scissurellidae (Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda) from tropical Indo-Pacific submarine caves. *The Veliger*, 45 (1): 25-32.